

Analysis of Marketing Strategy in Optimizing New Student Registration at the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi

Alreza Pri Nugraha^{1*}, R Deni Muhammad Danial², Darmo H. Suwiryo³

Master of Administrative Sciences, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi, Indonesia

*Corresponding author: pri Nugrahalreza@ummi.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the general marketing strategy used to attract prospective new students of the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi (UMMI). Data was collected through observation, document analysis, and interviews. This study uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach and applies Miles & Huberman's qualitative analysis to process the data. The results of the study show that the use of marketing mix dimensions (products, costs, places, promotions) by UMMI in optimizing the number of new student enrollment has resulted in several alternative strategies, including efforts to improve promotional strategies such as communicating advantages through hard selling, building an image through soft selling, and expand the reach of promotion and increase credibility through cooperative relationships with government agencies and other universities. Supporting factors include human resources, the existence of a scholarship system, and financial aid to provide opportunities for prospective students from diverse financial backgrounds to gain access to higher education. Adequate facilities and infrastructure, such as modern laboratories and a complete library, while the inhibiting factor is stiff competition with other universities offering similar programs and limited marketing budgets can also develop effective and extensive marketing campaigns.

Keywords: marketing strategy, marketing mix, promotion strategy.

Introduction

Education is considered a key pillar in shaping the future of a nation, while global competition drives the need to increase capacity and intelligence through high educational qualifications (Aliyyu, 2022). In this context, universities play a crucial role by providing a variety of study programs to meet the need for a quality workforce. The existence of universities in Indonesia is expected to enrich a variety of education ranging from Bachelor of Science to Master's, to Doctoral levels. Competition between universities to attract and retain the number of students is not easy, this requires the campus to develop a strategy and implement it carefully (Hughes et al., 2021).

Inter-campus competition to increase the interest of prospective students to register is one of the main challenges. Factors such as accreditation, the quality of teachers, and campus facilities are determinants in choosing a university. Given the competition for higher education services both at home and abroad, campuses must use business concepts as well as companies that adopt marketing strategies (Kusuma Widjaja, 2021; Shymko, 2018). Especially in the Vision

and mission, which is the key to moving the educational organization, and balancing with the right tactics and strategies to achieve superior quality for the university (Han et al., 2022).

In Sukabumi, the number of universities that stand is not much, the only campus that is in the city center and offers a variety of study programs that have good accreditation is the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi. This condition provides an opportunity for UMMI to increase the number of students on the campus. However, it is possible to fluctuate the increase in the number of new students on the campus, as evidenced by the latest data related to student enrollment and admissions, as shown in the table below:

Table 1. UMMI New Student Data Year 2019-2020 to 2023-2024

Year	Registrar	Registration	No Registration	Percentage %
2019-2020	1.497	1.204	293	19,6%
2020-2021	1.297	1.029	268	19,5%
2021-2022	1.557	1.144	413	26,5%
2022-2023	1.951	1.534	417	21,4%
2023-2024	1.560	1.095	465	29,8%
Sum	7.844	6.006	1.836	23,4%

Table 1 above explains the data on new student admissions to the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi in the last five years. The data shows that the average registrant in the last five years is 1,568, while the average number of registrants is 1,201. From the number of registrants and those who registered, there was a difference of 367 people who did not register. A significant decrease in registrants was in the 2020-2021 school year, while a significant decrease in registration was in 2020-2021 and 2023-2024. Likewise, the percentage of prospective students who did not register occurred from 2021-2022 to 2023-2024, where those who did not register were above 400 people. And overall in the last five years, there were 7844 registrants and 6006 registered, while 1,836 or 23.4% did not register.

Thus, there is a variation in the number of new student registrations every year, showing the complexity of the dynamics of student admissions at UMMI. Marketing in higher education emphasizes the fulfillment of the needs and desires of prospective students through the added value of educational products or services provided. Being customer-oriented is key, with a deep understanding of the needs and behaviors of prospective students as well as value creation and long-term relationships.

In the face of fluctuations in the number of new student registrations, the University considers it important to conduct a marketing strategy analysis to plan the right steps in achieving the institution's goals, especially to increase new student enrollment by using various types of relevant analysis (Maricic & Dordevic, 2014). This is necessary because education industry players need to fulfill the promises given to prospective students, considering that dissatisfaction can lead to challenges or complaints that can harm the reputation of the university. Implementing an effective marketing strategy is the main key to facing fierce competition in the competitive education industry. Therefore, the study of internal and external factors is very important to

develop the right marketing strategy, including the setting of the ideal price, distribution, promotion, and product mix. Strategic planning should consider the mission and program before choosing the right alternative strategy. Along with that, continuous efforts to conduct assessments and investigations will help produce better and ideal planning in increasing the number of new student admissions (Lane et al., 2022).

The problem phenomenon faced by the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi is the fierce competition between universities in attracting the interest of prospective new students, and the decrease in prospective students who will register, as well as the non-optimal strategy applied by universities to prospective students who have registered in the last five years. Based on the description and phenomenon above, this study aims to analyze marketing strategies in UMMI new student admissions and evaluate the effectiveness of strategies that have been implemented in attracting the interest of prospective new students.

Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy is a logical framework to achieve the marketing goals of a business unit (Gotteland et al., 2020). It is a comprehensive plan that integrates various elements of marketing to guide the steps to take to achieve the company's goals in the market. In general, a marketing strategy is a set of goals, policies, and rules that provide direction to a company's marketing efforts over time, adapting to the ever-changing environment and competition (Srinivasan & Lohith, 2017). Marketing strategy involves various activities that can affect consumer demand for products, such as price adjustments, changes in advertising strategies, development of unique promotions, selection of distribution channels, and so on (Azzadina et al., 2012). In reality, marketing plans are usually integrated or carried out simultaneously, and sometimes, due to resource limitations, marketing managers have to choose the most effective marketing program.

An organization's need for a marketing plan arises from its difficulty in managing external factors that affect its environment. Similarly, it is difficult to predict exactly how these factors will develop. The marketing strategy the main bid mission, marketing, and financial objectives, target audience, and demand are all determined by the product manager (Hollebeek & Macky, 2019). The manager will then decide how the product line will compete, which will influence the "game plan" to achieve that goal (Perdana et al., 2023). In terms of campus bureaucracy, all of this extends input from other fields or divisions, such as academics, finance, student affairs, and cooperation. Marketing strategy is to try to advertise a product or service by using several tactics and business plans to increase sales (Dewsnap et al., 2020). Marketing strategy is essentially a comprehensive, integrated, and integrated plan in the field of marketing that provides direction on the actions that must be taken to realize the marketing goals of a company (Samanta, 2022). The implementation of a plan or strategy requires the support of fundamental elements to ensure the success of the plan or strategy. Likewise, 4P marketing is a key component of the marketing process (price, place, product, and promotion) (Kotler and Keller, 2020).

If the 4 dimensions in the *marketing mix theory* are implemented properly, the right marketing strategy will be obtained to attract the interest of new student registrants at UMMI.

With the right marketing strategy, it will be able to optimize the increase in the number of registrations and UMMI's competitiveness in the higher education market, especially Sukabumi, and the National in general.

Method

The object of discussion in this study is the Marketing Strategy for Optimizing New Student Registration at the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi, while the informants are the Vice Chancellor III, the Head of UPT HPPMB, the Secretary and Treasurer of UPT HPPMB, the Staff of the Student Affairs Bureau of the PUKAU section, parents of prospective new students, prospective new students, with a total of 5 informants. This research method uses qualitative, where the research procedure can produce descriptive data, namely in the form of speech, behavior, and phenomena found when going directly into the field to observe the Object and Subject to be researched (Sugiyono, 2019). The purpose of qualitative research is to understand a particular social situation, event, role, group, or interaction, which is largely an investigative process. In which researchers gradually understand social phenomena by contrasting, comparing, replicating, cataloging, and classifying research objects (Creswell, 2023). The type of research used is descriptive, which is research that aims to decrypt or explain something as it is. This research aims to provide a description or overview of a situation. The data collection methods in this study are literature studies, observations, interviews, and documentation. To test the validity of the research data, triangulation techniques (sources, techniques, and time) are used which aim to obtain findings or interpretations accurately and credibly (Moleong, 2017). This study uses qualitative data analysis techniques, namely data analysis is carried out at the same time as data collection or during observation and interviews. The practical steps taken during data analysis are (1) data collection, if the data found in the field can exceed the author's wishes, the author must write the data in detail, because the longer the researcher goes into the field, the more complex the data will be obtained. (2) data presentation, namely collecting information, taking action, and presenting qualitative data either in the form of graphs, images, or tables, (3) data reduction, namely sharpening, classifying, discarding unnecessary information, and organizing data. and taking action. (4) data verification and conclusions, namely re-verifying the data and drawing conclusions from the data, the conclusion is taken when the data is saturated and every addition of new data only means overlapping (Miles & Huberman, 2018).

Analysis of Marketing Strategy in Optimizing New Student Registration at the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi

To be able to measure the success of marketing strategies in optimizing the number of new student admissions at the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi., the researcher uses 4 dimensions, including (1) *Product* (2) *Price* (3) *Place* (4) *Promotion* In addition to explaining how the marketing strategy is in optimizing the number of UMMI new student admissions, in

this discussion it is also explained about what are the supporting factors and obstacles in implementing the marketing strategy. The following is a description of the results of the study:

1) Product

The Freshman Acceptance Rate is a key metric in measuring product success. The number of applicants and new students accepted gives an idea of how attractive the products offered by the educational institution are. The higher the acceptance rate, the more effective the product is in attracting the interest of prospective students. The results of the interview with the Secretary and Treasurer of UPT HPPMB explained that:

“So far many prospective freshmen are interested and registered for the UMMI campus to choose the business administration study program, this study program is famous among prospective freshmen because it has A accreditation and every year the registrants are more than 200 people, 2 to 3 times more than other study programs at UMMI”.

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be interpreted that the Business Administration Study Program as one of the products on the UMMI Campus has successfully implemented an effective marketing strategy. A good reputation with accreditation, high demand from prospective students, and a much higher ratio of the number of applicants compared to other study programs on campus show that this study program has a strong attraction in the higher education market. This success is largely due to its competitive advantage, which includes the quality of education, facilities, faculty reputation, and solid industry connections.

The achievement of alumni after graduating from college can also be a key indicator of the success of the university's marketing strategy. As the interview statement answered by the Student Affairs Bureau Staff that I dug up the information said:

“There are several UMMI alumni who have succeeded, including The Nira Dwi Afriannisa who has worked and lived for 10 years participating in the Indonesia-Japan cooperation program in the field of elderly nursing, he is an alumnus of the D3 Nursing Study Program in 2011, there is Kang Maulana Ibrahim who graduated from Agribusiness in 2019, he works in one of the companies in the agricultural sector in Japan and there is also Kang Ridwan Darusalam who has a famous pastry bakery business "Bolu Amor" in his Sukabumi alumni of the Aquaculture Study Program in 2008. So there are already many UMMI alumni who have succeeded according to their respective achievements”.

The results of the UMMI alumni interviews above show that the career success achieved by alumni, such as occupying important positions in the industry, starting a successful business, or becoming leaders in their fields, reflects the quality of education they receive at the university. More than that, the recognition from the industry of alumni achievements emphasizes the relevance of campus education programs to the demands of the job market. The positive contributions made by alumni to society, whether through charitable activities, volunteer work, or advancing projects, also strengthen the image of the campus as a caring and socially responsible institution. With the campus reputation based on alumni achievements, the campus becomes more attractive to prospective students, strengthens its position in the competition in the world of higher education, and confirms the success of the marketing strategy that has been implemented.

2) Price

Pricing is very important for a university. The success of the marketing strategy can be reflected in the way the university sets the tuition fee. Proper pricing should take into account a variety of factors, such as operational costs, facilities provided, the reputation of the institution, and the needs of students and their families. As the results of an interview with one of the parents of prospective new students:

“we are a bit worried about the expensive tuition fees at UMMI. We feel the need to understand more about how this will affect our finances and the future of our children's education, we want to know if there are any scholarships, financial aid programs, or other possibilities that can help ease the burden of tuition fees, and we also want to make sure that the value of education at UMMI will be worth the cost we will incur”.

From the results of the interview above, there is an assumption that the tuition fee at UMMI is high, this is often a topic that is discussed among prospective students and the community. Some people may feel deterred by these high costs, seeing them as a barrier to their access to higher education. However, it should be emphasized that the high tuition fee also reflects the large investment from the campus in improving the quality of teaching, laboratory facilities, library, and curriculum development that is relevant to the demands of the industry and the job market. In this case, UMMI ensures that the tuition fees they set reflect the value of the education they provide. Costs that are too low may not be enough to cover operational costs and the provision of adequate facilities, while costs that are too high can make UMMI lose competitiveness and exclude many potential prospective students.

In determining the cost strategy, UMMI also pays attention to the financial needs of students and their families. The provision of scholarships or financial assistance from the government and community organizations can be one way to maintain the accessibility of higher education for talented but financially disadvantaged students.

Table 2. UMMI Student Tuition Fees in 2024

BIAYA PENDIDIKAN MAHASISWA KELAS REGULER UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SUKABUMI Tahun Akademik 2024/2025				
No	Program Studi	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 1-4)	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 5-6)	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 7-8)
1	SI Teknik Informatika	Rp. 1.222.600	Rp. 1.208.400	Rp. 883.500
2	SI Teknik Sipil	Rp. 1.205.100	Rp. 1.250.900	Rp. 883.500
3	SI Kimia	Rp. 1.303.600	Rp. 1.378.400	Rp. 883.500
		Rp. 888.850	Rp. 1.058.400	Rp. 563.500
4	SI Agribisnis	Rp. 1.200.100	Rp. 1.130.400	Rp. 883.500
5	SI Akuakultur	Rp. 1.200.100	Rp. 1.130.400	Rp. 883.500
		Rp. 786.350	Rp. 810.400	Rp. 563.500
6	SI Administrasi Bisnis	Rp. 1.155.100	Rp. 1.050.400	Rp. 883.500
7	SI Administrasi Publik	Rp. 1.194.100	Rp. 1.098.400	Rp. 883.500
8	SI Sastra Inggris	Rp. 1.321.600	Rp. 1.098.400	Rp. 883.500
9	SI Akuntansi	Rp. 1.192.600	Rp. 1.146.400	Rp. 883.500
10	D3 Perpajakan	Rp. 1.217.000	Rp. 658.500	-
		Rp. 709.500	Rp. 638.500	-
11	SI Manajemen Ritel	Rp. 1.172.600	Rp. 1.106.400	Rp. 883.500
12	SI PJKR	Rp. 1.260.000	Rp. 1.094.800	Rp. 883.500
13	SI Pendidikan Biologi	Rp. 1.299.000	Rp. 1.234.000	Rp. 883.500
		Rp. 886.150	Rp. 914.000	563.500
14	SI PGSD	Rp. 1.230.460	Rp. 1.047.320	Rp. 883.500
15	SI PG PAUD	Rp. 1.227.100	Rp. 1.029.000	Rp. 883.500
		Rp. 813.350	Rp. 709.000	563.500
16	SI Pend Teknologi Informasi	Rp. 1.295.700	Rp. 1.166.200	Rp. 883.500
		Rp. 881.950	Rp. 846.200	Rp. 563.500
17	SI Pend Matematika	Rp. 1.199.100	Rp. 973.000	Rp. 883.500
18	SI Pend Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia	Rp. 1.227.100	Rp. 1.029.000	Rp. 883.500
19	SI Ilmu Hukum	Rp. 1.206.350	Rp. 1.143.400	Rp. 883.500
20	D3 Keperawatan	Rp. 1.944.500	Rp. 1.263.500	-
21	SI Keperawatan	Rp. 1.897.600	Rp. 1.803.400	Rp. 1.143.500
22	Pendidikan Profesi Ners	Rp. 2.383.500	-	-

BIAYA PENDIDIKAN MAHASISWA
PROGRAM MAGISTER
UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SUKABUMI
Tahun Akademik 2024/2025

No	Program Studi	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 1)	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 2-3)	Biaya Per Bulan (Semester 4)
1	Magister Ilmu Administrasi	Rp. 3.390.000	Rp. 1.660.000	Rp. 1.550.000
2	Kelas Fasttrack Fakultas Ilmu Sosial	Rp. 1.970.000		Rp. 1.700.000

**Biaya tersebut sudah termasuk biaya SPP, Registrasi, Kegiatan Kemahasiswaan, Jns Abnawater, Praktikum, UTS/UAS, KKN, Magang/PKL/Ristik, dan biaya Tugas Akhir/Skripsi.*

**Untuk D3&S1 Keperawatan sudah termasuk juga untuk biaya Atribut dan Proses Angkat Janji, Alat Kesehatan (Untuk S1 Keperawatan), dan Pelatihan BTCLS (Untuk D3 Keperawatan).*

**Terdapat Beasiswa bebas biaya 1 bulan setiap semesternya, sehingga hanya membayar 3 bulan saja.*

In addition, transparency in pricing is also important. UMMI also clearly explains how tuition fees are calculated, including additional costs such as accommodation fees, lecture materials, or other administrative costs. Thus, prospective students and their families can make more mature decisions and prepare themselves better financially. As shown in the data below:

Application fee

Registration Fees for New Student Admissions at UMMI, including: All Study Programs (DIII/S1): Rp. 200,000,- (two hundred thousand rupiah), specifically for nursing study programs Rp. 300,000,- (three hundred thousand rupiah), Master's Study Program (S2) registration Rp. 500,000,- (five hundred thousand rupiah) Note: Each payment is added Rp. 2,000,- (two thousand rupiah) for bank administration fees.

3) Place

The place and location of a campus have a very important role in determining the success of a marketing strategy. In this case, buildings and supporting infrastructure play an important role in the success of a university's marketing strategy. Adequate physical facilities such as modern lecture buildings, laboratories equipped with the latest equipment, a library complete with learning resources, and adequate sports and recreation facilities are the main attractions for prospective students.

Investing in good infrastructure not only creates a comfortable learning environment but also makes a strong positive impression on prospective students and their parents. In addition, complete facilities also reflect the university's commitment to the quality of education and student welfare, which in turn can improve the image and reputation of the institution in the eyes of the public.

In addition, the location in particular, in the context of the UMMI campus, geographical factors, and the surrounding environment are aspects that need to be considered in depth. The location of the UMMI campus located in the city center has great potential to be one of the main factors in the success of the institution's marketing strategy. The existence of the campus in a strategic location allows for good accessibility for prospective students from various regions. Easily accessible public transportation facilities, such as city transportation, buses, online motorcycle taxis, and private vehicles, make the campus an attractive destination for those seeking higher education. Thus, the presence of a campus in the city center provides a significant

competitive advantage in marketing efforts. As the results of an interview with one of the students of a private high school in Sukabumi who is a prospective new UMMI student said:

"It seems that if you study at UMMI, it's really good in the middle of the city because the building is quite high, there is a large mosque, it is easy to access you can use anything if you go to campus, you can go anywhere without hassle, the environment will make the college experience more exciting, near the place to look for necessities, many cool hangout places to chill, so you can feel the campus life that is not monotonous. So I can manage my lecture time and leisure time more efficiently." (Main Informant 2).

In addition, the strategic location also allows the institution to more easily reach prospective students and facilitate various promotional activities. Marketing teams can easily organize recruitment events, such as open houses, seminars, and campus visits, which can pique the interest of prospective students. The presence of the campus in the city center also provides an opportunity to establish partnerships with local companies and organizations, thereby expanding the marketing network and increasing the visibility of the campus.

In addition to the practical aspect, the location of the campus in the city center can also improve the image and reputation of the institution. Presence in the middle of the center of economic, social, and cultural activities gives a prestigious impression that can increase the attractiveness of prospective students. This factor is important in building a positive perception of the campus in the eyes of the public and potential students. Furthermore, the campus's strategic location also allows the institution to integrate the surrounding environment into the student learning experience. Collaborations with local businesses, government agencies, and community organizations can enrich the student learning experience through internships, collaborative projects, and community service programs. This not only strengthens the bond between the campus and the local community but also increases the added value of the education provided by the institution.

By optimally utilizing the strategic location of the UMMI campus in its marketing strategy, the institution can increase its attractiveness to prospective students, strengthen its image and reputation, and expand its influence in the local community. As a result, the campus can achieve success in attracting new students and strengthening its position in the higher education market.

4) Promotion

Promotion plays a very crucial role in determining the success of a university's marketing strategy in the contemporary era which is filled with fierce competition. In a rapidly evolving and changing world, where prospective students have a wide variety of college options, effective promotion can be a key deciding factor in differentiating one college from another. Well-planned promotions carried out by UMMI not only help communicate the unique advantages possessed by a university but also create a strong impression in the minds of prospective students and encourage them to choose UMMI as a place to pursue their academic goals.

One of the important aspects of promotion in the context of higher education is its ability to build a strong image and brand of the institution through marketing strategies that are inclusive

promotional strategies, such as creative advertising campaigns, active presence on social media, participation in educational exhibition events, and collaboration with relevant parties in the industry, colleges can strengthen their identity and stand out among their competitors. A positive image and a strong brand not only make the university more attractive to prospective students, but also build trust and loyalty from other stakeholders, such as alumni, donors, and industry partners.

Effective promotion also helps colleges to expand their reach and reach the appropriate target market. By leveraging a variety of media and communication channels, from digital advertising to partnership programs with overseas education agencies, higher education institutions can increase their visibility globally and attract interest from prospective international students. In addition, targeted and focused promotions allow colleges to reach potential students across different demographic and geographic segments, expanding their application base and creating diverse and inclusive classes.

Promotion must be accompanied by a measurable and sustainable strategy to achieve optimal results. Universities need to continue to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the various promotional initiatives they run, as well as make continuous adjustments and improvements based on the data and feedback obtained. Thus, they can ensure that the resources invested in promotions generate optimal rates of return and contribute significantly towards the achievement of their long-term marketing goals.

The following are the results of the interview with the Vice Chancellor III as well as the acting Head of UPT HPPMB:

"Our main focus is to ensure that we are not only informing about our programs but also building strong relationships with prospective students and the surrounding community. We believe that a combination of hard selling, soft selling, and cooperation is the key to achieving these goals".

It is stated that currently UMMI uses 3 ways of marketing approaches to carry out promotions, namely:

a. *Hard Selling*

In the context of UMMI Campus promotion, *the hard-selling* approach can be implemented by prioritizing direct and persuasive communication to potential prospective students. For example, in advertising materials or presentations of educational exhibitions, the Ummi Campus can actively highlight its advantages such as program accreditation, modern facilities, or academic achievements. With this approach, the campus can emphasize the direct benefits that prospective students will get if they choose the Ummi Campus as their educational institution. Additionally, special sales tactics such as sign-up discounts or scholarship programs can be used to encourage immediate action from prospective students.

b. *Soft selling*

In the Marketing Approach, *soft selling* will emphasize more on building an image and strong relationships with prospective students and their families. Rather than emphasizing direct selling, promotions will focus more on a more subtle and persuasive approach. For example, the Ummi Campus can use educational and inspirational marketing content such as

presentation videos about unique learning experiences on campus, alumni success stories, or community-building student activities.

c. Cooperative Relations

In the context of cooperative relations in the promotion of the UMMI Campus, this approach can involve cooperation with industry, other educational institutions, and educational agents. UMMI Campus can establish partnerships with related companies or industries to provide internship opportunities, research collaborations, or career opportunities for students. In addition, the campus can collaborate with other educational institutions both at home and abroad for student exchanges, joint programs, or joint academic activities. This not only expands the reach of the campus's promotions but also enhances its reputation as an open and progressive institution. Partnerships with overseas education agencies can also be an effective promotional strategy for the Ummi Campus. By working with trusted educational agents, the campus can reach out to prospective international students and provide support in their on-campus application and adaptation process.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of Marketing Strategy for New Student Admissions of the University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi

1) Supporting Factors

There are several factors supporting the implementation of UMMI's marketing strategy to achieve success and optimize the number of new student registrations. The following are the supporting factors for the marketing strategy of UMMI's new student admissions found by the researcher through an interview with Vice Chancellor III:

“At UMMI, we attract prospective students with various advantages, such as relevant and interesting study programs and an inclusive scholarship system for diverse financial backgrounds. In addition, modern facilities and infrastructure, such as laboratories and libraries, provide a conducive learning environment. We are also active in marketing through social media and partnering with local high schools to increase visibility and reach out to potential students, which overall helps us increase the attraction and intake of new students.”

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be known that the supporting factors for the marketing strategy of UMMI new student admissions are as follows:

First, the excellence of the study programs offered is the main attraction for prospective students. By providing relevant and engaging study programs, universities can attract prospective new students who are looking for a quality education. Furthermore, the existence of a scholarship and financial aid system provides opportunities for prospective students from diverse financial backgrounds to gain access to higher education. Adequate facilities and infrastructure, such as modern laboratories and a complete library, are also important supporting factors in creating a conducive learning environment. In addition, the university has also used various effective marketing channels, including social media and educational seminars, to increase its visibility among prospective students. Lastly, active cooperation with local high schools has helped in disseminating information about the university and reaching out to potential students at an earlier

level. With the combination of these factors, Universitas Muhammadiyah Sukabumi can continue to increase its attractiveness and increase the number of new student admissions.

2) Inhibiting Factors

"I think one of the things we need to consider is the increasingly stiff competition with other universities offering similar programs. This can be a big barrier for us because prospective students have a lot of options. In addition, the limited budget for marketing also made us have to work with limited resources to reach prospective new students effectively. In addition, we must always monitor changes in government policies related to education as this can significantly affect our marketing strategy. Finally, the uncertainty of the external environment such as political and economic conditions can also be an obstacle for us in attracting prospective new students. We are working to overcome these obstacles with more innovative and results-oriented strategies, but we recognize that this is a challenge that we must face continuously".

As the results of the interview above, the Secretary of UPT HPPMB explained that even though UMMI has a strong marketing strategy, several inhibiting factors can still hinder its success in attracting new students. Stiff competition with other universities offering similar programs can be a significant challenge. Limited marketing budgets can also limit the university's ability to develop effective and far-reaching marketing campaigns. Changes in government policies related to education, such as new student admission policies or curriculum changes, can also significantly affect the university's marketing strategy. External environmental uncertainties, such as political or economic instability at the local or national level, can also be a barrier to attracting prospective new students. By identifying and overcoming these obstacles, Universitas Muhammadiyah Sukabumi can improve the effectiveness of its marketing strategy and remain competitive in recruiting new students.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the conclusion is as follows: UMMI new student admissions if implementing a marketing strategy with the marketing mix method (*Marketing Mix*), this is reviewed from the dimensions. 1) Product: UMMI has succeeded in implementing an effective marketing strategy, as evidenced by the Business Administration Study Program whose new student acceptance rate is in great demand by prospective new students and impressive alumni achievements and achievements in the world of work and business both domestically and abroad. 2) Price: Setting the right tuition fee also reflects the success of the marketing strategy. UMMI pays attention to operational costs, facilities, institutional reputation, and financial needs of students. Although the tuition fee at UMMI is high, UMMI emphasizes the value of education that is balanced with financial accessibility. Transparency in pricing, including financial aid options, is also demonstrated. Thus, UMMI maintains competitiveness while ensuring balanced educational accessibility for students. Place. 3) Campus places and locations, especially strategic ones in the city center such as the UMMI campus, have an important role in the university's marketing strategy. Adequate physical facilities

and good accessibility attract the interest of prospective students. In addition, the strategic location enhances the image of the institution, expands the marketing network, and enriches the student learning experience through integration with the surrounding environment. By making optimal use of the campus location, the institution can increase its attractiveness, strengthen its image and reputation, and achieve success in attracting new students. 4) *Promotion*: By using a mix of promotional strategies such as *hard selling*, *soft selling*, and cooperative relationships, Ummi Campus can strengthen its image and attract the interest of prospective students effectively. This allows the campus to directly communicate excellence through *hard selling*, build an image through *soft selling*, expand the reach of promotion, and increase credibility through cooperative relationships. By combining these three approaches, the Ummi Campus can achieve optimal results in its promotional efforts. Thus, UMMI has succeeded in implementing a comprehensive and effective marketing strategy to increase its attractiveness to attract prospective new students, maintain competitiveness, and ensure balanced educational accessibility for students.

To maintain the excellence and attractiveness of the institution, UMMI needs to continue to pay attention to several important aspects in its marketing strategy and educational services, including 1) Continuous efforts in improving the quality of education and facilities at UMMI must ensure that the products or graduates produced can easily integrate into the world of work or become successful entrepreneurs by their fields. This will make UMMI an attractive choice for prospective new students because they can be sure that investment in education at UMMI will provide good results and by expectations. 2) Institutions should consider flexibility in pricing and offer more scholarships with diverse criteria to remain accessible to all walks of life. 3) Optimizing the use of strategic campus locations which will be an added value in strengthening the image and attractiveness of the institution. 4) Developing innovative promotion strategies, such as collaboration with educational institutions and companies that accept UMMI graduates as a workforce, can contribute to achieving maximum success in attracting the interest of prospective students.

References

- Aliyyu, A. (2022). Mengenal Fenomena Disruptive Behaviour dalam Dunia Pendidikan. UPI Press.
- Azzadina, I., Huda, A. N., & Sianipar, C. P. M. (2012). Understanding the Relationship between Personality Types, Marketing-mix Factors, and Purchasing Decisions. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 65(ICIBSoS), 352–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.133>
- Creswell, J. W. (2023). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (6th ed.). Sage Publications Inc.
- Dewsnap, B., Micevski, M., Cadogan, J. W., & Kadic-Maglajlic, S. (2020). Flexibility in marketing & sales interfacing processes. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 91, 285–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.09.005>

- Gotteland, D., Shock, J., & Sarin, S. (2020). Strategic orientations, marketing proactivity, and firm market performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 91, 610–620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.03.012>
- Han, W., Zhou, Y., & Lu, R. (2022). Strategic orientation, business model innovation, and corporate performance—Evidence from the construction industry. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.971654>
- Hollebeek, L. D., & Macky, K. (2019). Digital Content Marketing’s Role in Fostering Consumer Engagement, Trust, and Value: Framework, Fundamental Propositions, and Implications. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 45, 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.07.003>
- Hughes, R., Dahlin, L., & Tucci, T. (2021). An Investigation of a Multiple-Measures Teaching Evaluation System and Its Relationship with Students’ College-Going Outcomes. *Educational Policy*, 35(1), 131–158. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904818813302>
- Kotler and Keller. (2020). *Marketing Management (15th ed.)*. Pearson Education, inc.
- Kusuma Widjaja, M. E. L. (2021). Strategic Orientation and Human Resources Management in Public Sector Organizations in the Society 5.0 Era. *Proceedings of the 18th International Symposium on Management*, 18(1), 235–240.
- Lane, C., Nathan, N., Reeves, P., Sutherland, R., Wolfenden, L., Shoesmith, A., & Hall, A. (2022). Economic evaluation of a multi-strategy intervention that improves school-based physical activity policy implementation. *Implementation Science*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-022-01215-6>
- Maricic, B. R., & Dordevic, A. (2014). Strategic Market Segmentation. *Marketing*, 21(1), 243–251.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (2018). *Qualitative Data Analysis (4th ed.)*. Sage Publications.
- Moleong, L. J. (2017). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Perdana, S., Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Vielle, M., Nikas, A., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Anger-Kraavi, A., May, E., McWilliams, B., & Boitier, B. (2023). Expert perceptions of game-changing innovations towards net zero. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2022.101022>
- Samanta, I. (2022). Examining relationship marketing and strategic branding in b2b Greek SMEs: A family business development. *Innovative Marketing*, 18(3), 110–120. [https://doi.org/10.21511/im.18\(3\).2022.10](https://doi.org/10.21511/im.18(3).2022.10)
- Shymko, V. (2018). Object field of organizational culture: methodological conceptualization. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 26(4), 602–613. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-03-2017-1135>
- Srinivasan, R., & Lohith, C. P. (2017). *Strategic Marketing and Innovation for Indian MSMEs*. <http://www.springer.com/series/11234>
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R dan D*. Alfabeta.

